
Role Of Youth Empowerment In “Viksit Bharat”

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Abstract:

India is at a turning point in his history. Where currently Indian economy is the 5th largest economy with GNI of approximately \square 3.5 trillion USD, positioning it to become the world's third-largest economy by 2027. Rest top four economies are developed, India is the fastest growing developing economy compared to them. By launching the ‘Viksit Bharat’ by 2047, marking 100 years of independence, the government is planning to achieve sustainable growth, innovation with advanced technology, from promoting export to generating employment, building infrastructure etc., under this goal.

My research paper is reviewing the way ahead to achieve the vision of ‘Viksit Bharat’ but at the same time the role of youth empowerment, transparency and good governance, equal opportunities for women in it.

Keywords: *Youth Empowerment, Strategic Investment, Women Empowerment, Education, Discrimination.*

Introduction:

In 1947, when the Britishers left India, they left behind a broken, needy, underdeveloped, and economically weaker country. The immediate task at hand was to handle the challenges of basic survival. This was the priority. For the first few decades after independence, governments at all levels, be it Centre or State, were focused on addressing the challenges of poverty, ignorance and diseases. In the early period of post-independence India adopted a mixed economy model, combining elements of socialism and capitalism. The government focused on industrialization, agricultural growth, and self-sufficiency. The First Five-Year Plan (1951-56) primarily focused on agricultural development, while subsequent plans aimed to industrialize the economy. The green revolution resulted in increasing food security and economic growth. Alleviating hunger, malnutrition and poverty. The late 1980s and early 1990s marked a pivotal shift in India’s economic policies. Faced with a balance of payments crisis, the Indian government initiated economic liberalization measures in 1991. Deregulation, liberalized policies attracted foreign investment, leading to rapid economic growth.

Today India is the 5th largest economy in the world with \$4.27 trillion USD of GDP, accounting for 8.23% of global GDP. In recent years, India has seen a whopping rise of approximately 15,400 in the number of startups, which rose from 471 in 2016 to 72,993 as of June 2022. This phenomenal rise in startups has also produced millions of new jobs in the country. In terms of literacy rate, the quality of higher education is still a cause of major concern. Education stands as the cornerstone for empowering our youth. Access to quality education, tailored to meet the evolving needs of the 21st century, is the foundation upon which the future of India will be built.

With the largest youth population in the world, India can achieve wonders if its youth get equipped with proper skills and education. The youth can spearhead the creation of a vibrant startup ecosystem that fosters job creation, economic inclusivity, and technological advancements. By encouraging innovation and providing support, we can unleash the latent entrepreneurial spirit of our youth. India's youth requires concerted efforts from all stakeholders. It demands a collaborative approach involving government, educational institutions, private enterprises, and civil society organizations. Policies must be crafted to foster an ecosystem that nurtures talent, rewards innovation, and provides equal opportunities for all.

Objectives:

1. To understand the role of youth in our vision of 'Viksit Bharat'
2. To identifying the hurdles in achieving the goal
3. To channelise the potential of youth
4. To understand the role of stakeholders
5. To build platform for youth to get the assistance

Hypothesis:

“Youth empowerment programs have no significant impact on India's socio-economic development.”

“Investing in youth education and skill development plays a crucial role in India's vision of a developed nation.”

Sources of Data Collection:

Secondary both methods were used in this paper. In primary method interview and questionnaire method used. Secondary method involves government reports, data, research, literature, social media and web analytics.

Agriculture is one of the primary sectors in the Indian economy accounting for 15 to 18% of total GDP. Secondary sector includes major industries like textile, steel, cement, pharmaceuticals etc., contributes around 25 to 30% to the total GDP. The tertiary sector also known as the service sector holds the largest share in GDP around 55 to 60%. Comparing all this sectors with developed economy like China and USA.

Contribution of GDP (% of GDP)

Sector (Approx)	India (Approx)	USA (Approx)	China (Approx)
Primary (Agriculture, mining, fishing)	15-18%	~1%	~7-8%
Secondary (Manufacturing , industry)	25-30%	18-20%	~40%
Tertiary (Services)	55-60%	~80%	~52-55%

Employment by Sector (% of workforce)

Sector	India (Approx)	USA (Approx)	China (Approx)
Primary	~40%	~1-2%	~25%
Secondary	~25%	~20%	~28%
Tertiary	~35%	~78%	~47%

In India, the working age population is typically between individuals aged 15 to 64 years. Breakdown of working-age population in India:

1. Youth (15-24 years):
Entering the workforce, often involved in **education or early employment**.
2. Prime Working Age (25-54 years):
Most **economically productive group** with stable jobs and higher income potential.
3. Older Working Age (55-64 years):
Approaching **retirement** but still active in the labor market.

The working age population is over 961 million with a median age of 29 years indicating a relatively young workforce. Potential demographic dividend because of the **large and young working-age** population.

Despite the fact shown in the above table, a significant portion of its working-age population in India remains employed in the non-productive agricultural sector, claims the latest report prepared jointly by the International Labour Organization (ILO) - UN body of labour rights issues and Institute of Human Development.

Female Labour Force Participation Rate, or FLFPR, had increased over the past seven years from 23.3% in 2017-18 to 41.7% in 2023-24, the survey says.

Why are we lacking behind?

1. Education-employment relation:

According to recent data the current unemployment rate in India is 8.30 as per the Centre of Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE). The privilege of upper and upper-middle class to afford higher education and skills. Middle-lower and lower class stuck with low skills employment. The gap between skills provided by the education system and demand of the market and employers sometimes leads to educated but unemployed individuals. Structural changes like automation, technical advancement requires certain skills. Rapid population growth, seasonal employment, inadequate infrastructure, informal sector dominance, government policy etc.

2. Infrastructure Deficiency:

Compared to developed countries India is far behind in terms of progress in its infrastructure in roads, power, internet connectivity etc., which limits its industrial growth and investment which hampers business growth and job creation.

3. Low Investment in Health & Education:

Low investment in healthcare results in illness, malnutrition, and low life expectancy in work-age group. An unhealthy workforce is less productive. Insufficient funding in education leads to inadequate infrastructure, lack of practical skills training, outdated curriculum.

4. Poor standard of living:

Due to low income and wages inequality, a large segment of the population is engaged in low-paying informal sector jobs without any job security or benefits. Preventing them to rise

above the poverty line. According to the latest NFHS (2019-21), only 60.3% of households living in pucca, while 34% were semi-pucca and 4.6% were kutcha in 2019-21. Although the multidimensional poverty rate in India has declined significantly from 29.17% in 2013-14 to 11.28% in 2022-23, indicating a substantial improvement in living standards.

5. Social Issues:

Although the government is working very hard, still evil issues like caste practices, religion-region biases, gender discrimination, customs etc., exist in India which restrict access to the youth. It also tampers the mind and confidence of youth in society. Sometimes which leads to exploitation against them in the form of violence, humiliation.

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Government Initiatives for Youth Empowerment:

The Indian government has launched several initiatives and policies to empower youth, focusing on education, skill development, entrepreneurship, employment and leadership. Some of the key initiatives includes:

1. Skill India Mission: Aims to train over 400 million people in different skills by 2022. Programs like Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) provide free skill training and certification.
2. Start-ups India: Encourages entrepreneurship with benefits like tax exemptions, easier compliance, and funding support through the Fund of Funds for Start-ups (FFS).

3. Atal Innovation Mission (AIM): Promotes innovation and entrepreneurship through Atal Tinkering Labs in schools and Atal Incubation Centres for start-ups.
4. National Education Policy (NEP) 2020: Focuses on flexible curriculum, skill development, and vocational training from an early stage, aiming to make education more relevant to job markets.
5. Digital India: Enhances digital literacy and access, providing youth with better opportunities for education and employment in the tech sector.
6. National Youth Policy 2014: Aims to empower youth by focusing on education, employment, entrepreneurship, health and sports.
7. Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY): Offers collateral-free loans to young entrepreneurs to start or expand their businesses.
8. National Apprenticeship Promotion Scheme (NAPS): Encourages skill development through apprenticeships with financial incentives to industries.
9. Fit India and Khelo India: Promote sports and fitness among youth, offering opportunities for scholarships and professional sports training.

Suggestions:

1. Digital literacy and Access: Expanding the Digital India initiative to ensure internet access in remote locations. Provide affordable smartphones and data plans to bridge the gap of digital divide.
2. Quality Education for All the Spheres of Society: Improving the access to a quality of education especially in rural location. Investing in school infrastructure, digital learning tools, teacher - training programs.
3. Mental Health and Counselling: Awareness programs for mental health in school and colleges. Reducing the stigma around mental health issues through national campaigns.
4. Monitoring Body: We need strong monitoring body to monitor the various government initiatives and programs which also can do collection of data, displaying it and check the effectiveness of the programs. Reaching to the ground level and having an approach of bottom to top is more important.
5. Political and Civic Engagement: Encouraging the youth for participation in local governance and decision making will leads to transparency. Promoting platforms for young leaders to voice their opinion on policies.
6. Social Entrepreneurship and Volunteering: Promote social entrepreneurship by addressing issues like waste management, education, and healthcare. Create awareness about addiction issues.
7. Financial Literacy and Inclusion: Include financial literacy in school and college curricula to teach saving, investments and budgeting.
8. Gender Equality and Women Empowerment: Promote STEM education for girls and women-specific entrepreneurship programs. Ensure safety, equality and opportunities for women.

Conclusion:

Youth empowerment refers to the quality education, skill development, entrepreneurship opportunities, digital access and active participation of youth in governance can improve their potential effectively. But at the same time it is important to address challenges such as gender inequality, financial literacy, mental health awareness and addictions. We need collective efforts from the government, private sector and civil society plays a crucial role for creating an

environment where young people can thrive, innovate, and lead towards a brighter future. Investing in youth is not just an option but a necessity for inclusive and long-term growth of Viksit Bharat.

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